

Consumption of dark chocolate on middle mountains improves endothelial function in young healthy people: separate and observational study

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Abstract:

Introduction : The aim of this study was to assess the effect of the introduction of dark chocolate on the function of endothelium and vascular healthy and young populations.

The methods. A separate and observant study was conducted involving 30 healthy young people of Kyrgyz nationality, with an average age of 18.99 to 1.02 years, divided into three groups: the control group (CG) and Intervention Group (IG). IG was exposed to eating 8g/day 80% cocoa chocolate per month. All people were subjected to two clinical assessments, basal and after one month of intervention in which their weight, height, body mass index (BMI), systolic blood pressure (SAD), diastolic blood pressure (DAD), heart rate (CHS)) and dilatation (foot-and-mouth disease) were assessed. In the second moment, glycemia was also evaluated.

Results: CG and IG groups had similar baseline clinical and demographic characteristics. % vs. 13 to 6% respectively for IG and CG; $p < 0.001$). Endothelial function improved in IG after 1 month of flavonoid intake, with foot-and-mouth disease increased from 13 to 5% (original level) to 23 to 7% (after intervention; $p < 0.001$), with no significant differences in CG. There were no significant changes in BMI, blood pressure, heart rate and glycemia.

Conclusion: Daily consumption of 8 g / day 80% chocolate cocoa per month improves the endothelial function of young people, improving endothelial-dependent vasodilating.

Keywords:

Endothelial function, dilation, flavonoids, dark chocolate

Approach to vasopressor medications in shock states

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Abstract:

Introduction: Vasopressors are medications that causes vasoconstriction; some of them have additional inotropic effect. By maintaining end-organ perfusion; the role of vasopressors remains critical to prevent irreversible organ injury and failure, and their use is usually accompanied by fluid resuscitation for adequate patient outcomes. Vasopressor agents are used clinically in the treatment of arterial hypotension in shock states. Shock is best defined as inadequate blood flow to meet the metabolic needs of the tissues. The most common reasons for shock are the cardiac output is low relative to the global demand, despite increased O₂ extraction by the tissues; or perfusion pressure is inadequate such that blood flow distribution to metabolically active tissues is inadequate, despite an otherwise adequate cardiac output.

Conclusion : Shock requires timely fluid resuscitation and vasopressor therapy that constitutes the cornerstone of therapy. Prompt recognition of reversible factors of refractory shock, such as metabolic and electrolyte derangements, source control for septic shock and lung-protective mechanical ventilation for respiratory failure are important therapeutic adjuncts; norepinephrine is indicated in septic shock.

In cardiogenic shock complicating AMI, current guidelines based on expert opinion recommend dopamine or dobutamine as first-line agents with moderate hypotension (systolic blood pressure 70 to 100 mm Hg) and norepinephrine as the preferred therapy for severe hypotension (systolic blood pressure <70 mm Hg).

Norepinephrine is considered the first-line vasopressor in vasodilatory shock, dobutamine the firstline inotrope in shock associated with decreased cardiac output, and their combination in vasodilatory shock with decreased cardiac output. Epinephrine is the first-line catecholamine in anaphylactic shock; in cardiopulmonary resuscitation and also as second line in shock that is unresponsive to other catecholamines. Vasopressin is emerging as a therapy in resistant vasodilatory shock.

The efficiency of combined therapy of verapamil and indapamide in patients with metabolic syndrome

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Abstract:

The study aims: To study the effect of combination therapy with verapamil and indapamide on blood pressure (BP), the state of carbohydrate, and lipid and electrolyte metabolism in patients with metabolic syndrome (MS).

Material and methods: We examined 18 women with MS aged 41-66 years. During 12 weeks, they were prescribed a combination of verapamil (Russia) 80 mg 2 times a day and indapamide (Indap, PRO.MED.CS Praha a.s.) 2.5 mg 1 time per day. Before and after treatment, all patients carried out to 24-hour blood pressure monitoring (BPM), studied the lipid profile, and determined levels of electrolytes and glucose.

Results: The target level of systolic blood pressure (SBP) was achieved in 90% of patients, diastolic blood pressure (DBP) - in 75%. According to the ABPM, this combination effectively reduced the levels of SBP, DBP and pulse blood pressure, as well as indices of time and area of blood pressure, without negative impact on the blood pressure profile. The drugs did not worsen the indicators of carbohydrate, lipid, and electrolyte metabolism.

Conclusion: A high antihypertensive efficiency and metabolic neutrality of the combination of verapamil and indapamide allow to use in patients with MS.

Rare embolization of atypical case presentation

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Abstract:

Atrial Fibrillation is the most common cardiac arrhythmia in the general population and in patients with cardiovascular diseases. Also, it has a negative social impact because of its association with stroke, thromboembolism phenomenon and myocardial infarction. Thrombosis is mostly generated in the left atrial appendages then it may circulate in the systemic circulation.

Our case is an old male patient not known to have any chronic illness, presented previously to ophthalmic department due to sudden loss of vision and diagnosed as Central Retinal Artery Occlusion. All workup was done including cardiac consultation which show free study. After 6 months, the patient was presented to ER complaining of repeated attack of dizziness, nausea and vomiting. Examination show irregular irregular pulse and ECG confirmed Atrial Fibrillation as diagnosis.

Keywords:

Atrial fibrillation, arrhythmia, loop recorder, cardiology, heart, dizziness, embolization, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, thromboembolism, atrial appendage, ophthalmology, retinal artery, ECG.

Late Pulmonary Valve Replacement Post Repair of Tetralogy of Fallot

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Abstract:

Chronic pulmonary regurgitation (PR) post repair of Tetralogy of Fallot (TOF) has a deleterious effect on the right ventricular (RV) geometry and function. Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance (CMR) imaging emergent as a golden standard for quantitative assessment of pulmonary regurgitation and RV volumes and function Pulmonary valve replacement (PVR) in timely fashion is essential for regain of RV function

Aim of the study: A retrospective review of all cases of TOF repaired between 1985 to 2013 at Heart Center, King Faisal Specialist Hospital and Research Center, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

A total of 557 patients were included. Cases of pulmonary atresia were excluded. Patients were classified into two groups;

- Group1: who required trans annular patch (TAP)
- Group2: who had pulmonary valve sparing (PVS).

The two groups were compared as regards to the incidence and freedom duration for late pulmonary valve replacement (PVR).

Results: Pulmonary Valve Replacement

Late pulmonary valve replacement (PVR) was done for 17.3% of total patients

Incidence was higher in TAP (21% vs 3.3%; $p < 0.001$)

Freedom duration from PVR was significantly longer in PVS group ($p = 0.001$)

Conclusions: Pulmonary valve sparing in TOF repair has a protective effect on long term RV function with a less need for PVR. Sparing of the pulmonary valve function during TOF repair should be attempted by the surgeons when it is possible.

Coronary restenosis- what we have learned?

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Abstract:

Percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) technology developed over past four decades revolutionized the treatment pattern of obstructive coronary artery disease. Despite significant advancement in the technique, equipment and pharmacotherapy, target lesion failure in the form of restenosis remains the Achilles heel of a PCI approach.

When Andreaz Gruntzig introduced percutaneous Tran's luminal coronary intervention for the first time, despite the very selective use of procedures to proximal, short, non-calcified and concentric lesion subsets, the procedural success was low and complications rate high.

The advent of bare metal stent put a new horizon in the early 90s and improved outcomes over plain balloon angioplasty. However, soon it become realized that benefits of metallic scaffolds still have a major setback with significantly high incidence of restenosis within the stented segments.

Then it was the drug eluting stent technology that became the default strategy for the most of the coronary interventions. With successive generations with better platforms, different anti proliferative agents, newer polymer, improved stent design and thinner metallic struts, that lead to superior results in terms of target lesion failure and revascularization, myocardial infarction and stent thrombosis.

Despite all the technological advancement, stent failure in the form of in-stent restenosis occurs in 5- 10% cases of PCI procedures in a year and certain lesion subsets have particularly higher incidence rate of events. Every interventional cardiologist has to face this entity on a routine basis and there is no clear solution for this. Better lesion assessment with the help of intracoronary imaging will provide better insights and permits more focused therapy to treat such disease. The repeat revascularization procedure often requires additional therapy in form of repeat stent or application of drug coated balloons. Recurrent restenosis has nothing to offer percutaneous by repeated metal stents, rather to go for coronary artery bypass surgery.

Figure 1: Recurrent ISR in left anterior descending artery

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Dextrocardia with Atrial Septal Defect (ASD), Scoliosis and Spina Bifida: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Introduction: Dextrocardia is anomaly in the position of the heart, the heart is in the right hemithorax with the right and caudal base-apex of the heart. Dextrocardia is usually a single congenital disorder or can be accompanied by malposition of other organs such as liver and spleen.

Figure 1: Dextrocardia and scoliosis in patient

Case Illustration: A 1-month-old baby entered the hospital with complaints of dyspnea. The patient appeared to be sick with pulse 130x / minute, respiratory rate 62x / minute, temperature 36.5 0C, SPO2 70%. Physical examination showed tachypnea, intercostal retraction, systolic sigh and spina bifida. Radiography examination showed dextrocardia and scoliosis. A echocardiography examination showed ASD with a hole size 0.3 mm. The given treatment were Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, CPAP with 7 liter PEEP and 40% FIO2, NACL IVFD 0.9% 25cc / hour, then replaced with dextrose 5% NACL 0.225, Ampicillin injection 235 mg / 12 hours and breast milk 25 cc / 3 hour / OGT.

Figure 2: Echocardiography showed atrial

Discussion: Dextrocardia is a congenital disorder caused by malformation characterized by the position of the heart on the right. In this case, dextrocardia with ASD was found. From the history carried out on the patient's parents found several risk factors that cause congenital abnormalities, such as the first found genetic factor derived from the baby's family, exposure to pollutants and a history of poor nutrition during pregnancy.

Conclusion: Dextrocardia is anomaly in the position of the heart, the heart is in the right hemithorax with the base and apex of the jaws directed to the right and caudal. In this case dextrocardia with ASD was found. This disorder is caused by risk factor, genetic

Figure 3: Spina bifida in patient

Keywords:

Dextrocardia, Atrial Septal defect, sScoliosis, spina bifida, echocardiography

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The Evaluation of Left Atrium as a Heart Failure evolution predictor in patients with Arterial Hypertension

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Abstract:

About 50 Arterial Hypertension patients with developed Heart Failure were examined: left atrium ECG and Echocardiogram changes were estimated comparatively in dynamics. It is well known, that in patients with Arterial Hypertension developed changes of the Left Ventricle End-Diastolic pressure manifest not only in the Left Ventricle but in Left Atrium also. So that diastolic dysfunction and systolic dysfunction both increase the loading of the Left Atrium. By the cause of the Left Atrium muscle weakness comparatively with Left Ventricle muscle, it manifests firstly by functional and structure disturbances of the Left Atrium. We investigated these disturbances in patients with Arterial Hypertension by evaluation of their Electrocardiogram and Echocardiogram indices in dynamics. Ongoing research comparing ECG and Echocardiogram changes gave us the opportunity to reveal Left Atrium ECG disturbances relatively earlier than Echocardiogram structural changes. Many times when we revealed ECG signs of Left Atrium enlargement and loading, we did not observe any changes of the Echocardiogram indices at the early period.

Performed investigations in Arterial Hypertension patients with Heart Failure give the possibility to observe appropriate ECG changes firstly. These changes may be the early predictor of the possible developing Heart Failure in such patients, moreover it makes possible an optimal Arterial Hypertension management retarding and delaying the origin of the Heart Failure.